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STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING OF STUDENTS IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS 21ST CENTURY SKILLS

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Abstract: *In this article , the skills of the 21st century, the role of the skills of the 21st century in the development of society, the main importance of the development of the skills of the 21st century in today's education system, methods of effectively introducing these skills into the curriculum in general education schools, general strategies for developing 21st century skills of students in educational schools are presented.*

Keywords: *21st century skills, competence, critical thinking, creativity, communication, collaboration, information literacy, innovation, flexibility, problem solving, science, technology, engineering, art and math, basic skills.*

Introduction

In the industrial age, the main skills that determined human success were reading, writing and arithmetic. In the 21st century, the main focus is shifting to other skills: the ability to communicate with others and work in a team, leadership, creative and critical thinking, the ability to work with changes and achieve results.

These skills are described by the World Economic Forum in 3 categories:

Basic literacy reflects how students apply basic skills in their daily activities. These skills play a key role in students, enabling them to develop more advanced and important competencies and personal qualities. These skills include not only reading and arithmetic, but also scientific literacy, ICT literacy, financial literacy, cultural and civic literacy. Traditional education has focused primarily on acquiring these skills, but these skills are now the foundation for developing 21st century skills.

Competencies explains how students approach complex problems. For example, critical thinking is the ability to clarify, analyze, and evaluate situations, ideas, and information to solve problems. Creativity is the ability to imagine and find innovative approaches to problems, answer questions or use knowledge in different ways. Communicates and collaborates, communicates information and collaborates with others to solve problems. These competencies are critical for the 21st century workforce. Thus, critical analysis, knowledge transfer and teamwork will be the standard for the workforce of the future.

Personality traits reflect how students respond to changing environments. Personal qualities such as resistance to obstacles, flexibility and success in a rapidly changing market environment. Curiosity and initiative are the starting point for discovering new concepts and ideas. Leadership and sociocultural awareness involve building social, moral, and cultural relationships with others in a constructive manner. These skills are the keys to success in life for people in the 21st century. Our goal is to instill these skills in children from school age and give them the knowledge and skills that will help them become successful individuals.

21st century skills include the skills, abilities, and learning dispositions needed by educators, business leaders, scientists, and government agencies to succeed in 21st century society and the workplace. It is part of a growing international movement to develop the skills students need to prepare for success in a rapidly changing digital society. Many of these skills are also related to deeper learning based on the acquisition of skills such as analytical thinking, complex problem solving and teamwork. These skills differ from traditional academic skills in that they are not primarily based on content knowledge.

4 K skills of the 21st century. Communication, collaboration, critical thinking and creativity are the four K's (Communication, collaboration, critical thinking and creativity) and are the skills needed to succeed today.

These skills are very important for students and enable them to solve problems, work together and find solutions.

skills is critical to your child's success in school and beyond. So what are the four K's and how can we teach them to students?

1. Communication: exchange of ideas and opinions with the help of questions.

It is important to teach children that communication can take different forms. During communication, not only verbal communication is important, but also signs such as hand gestures and facial expressions. As we now live in the digital age, teaching children to be responsible in the digital space is the need of the hour.

2. Collaboration: working together to achieve a common goal.

Success in life requires people to work together. Children should also learn to solve their own problems from an early age. Young children's understanding of others' points of view is a bit more complicated. Developing these skills takes time and skill.

3. Critical thinking: a new approach to problems.

Part of criticism, that is, critical thinking, is problem solving, solving mind-boggling puzzles, and asking "why?" is to ask a question. In today's world where information is available at the click of a button, it is important to be able to determine whether information is reliable or not.

4. Creativity: trying new approaches to solving problems.

students are interested in art, they think more about creativity. Creativity means thinking out of the box, and it can be found in every field. Creativity can be fostered in children by encouraging them to try new things.

Why are these skills important?

4 K skills are closely related. Children need to acquire skills in four areas to be successful in the future. Employers look for candidates with exactly these skills.

These skills go beyond traditional academic knowledge and include the combination of cognitive, social, and emotional competencies needed to succeed in the modern workforce and society.

Understanding 21st Century Skills

Definition: 21st-century skills refer to a set of abilities that students need to thrive in today's rapidly changing world. These skills go beyond traditional academic

knowledge and encompass a combination of cognitive, social, and emotional competencies essential for success in the modern workforce and society.

Key 21st Century Skills

1. **Critical Thinking:** The ability to analyze information, evaluate arguments, and make informed decisions.
2. **Creativity:** Thinking innovatively, generating new ideas, and approaching problems from different perspectives.
3. **Communication:** Expressing ideas effectively through various mediums and engaging in active listening.
4. **Collaboration:** Working cooperatively with others, valuing diverse perspectives, and contributing to shared goals.
5. **Information Literacy:** Finding, evaluating, and using information from various sources critically.
6. **Technological Literacy:** Understanding and utilizing technology effectively to enhance learning and productivity.
7. **Adaptability:** Being flexible and open to change, learning new skills, and adjusting to different situations.
8. **Cultural Competence:** Respecting and understanding cultural differences, fostering inclusivity, and working across diverse teams.
9. **Problem-Solving:** Identifying challenges, developing solutions, and implementing strategies to overcome obstacles.
10. **Global Awareness:** Recognizing global issues, understanding interconnectedness, and appreciating diverse perspectives.

Importance of 21st Century Skills

- **Employability:** Employers seek candidates with strong 21st-century skills to navigate complex work environments and contribute effectively to their organizations.
- **Lifelong Learning:** Developing these skills prepares students to adapt to evolving technologies and industries throughout their lives.
- **Citizenship:** Equipping individuals with 21st-century skills fosters active participation in society, promoting social responsibility and civic engagement.

By cultivating 21st-century skills in students, educators empower them to become lifelong learners, critical thinkers, and collaborative problem-solvers capable of succeeding in a dynamic and interconnected world.

Importance of Teaching 21st Century Skills in Education

1. **Relevance to the Modern World.** Teaching 21st-century skills ensures that students are equipped with the competencies needed to thrive in a rapidly changing and technologically advanced society.

2. **Preparation for the Future Workforce.** By emphasizing 21st-century skills, educators prepare students for jobs that require critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and adaptability in diverse industries.

3. **Promotion of Innovation and Creativity.** Fostering skills like creativity and innovation encourages students to think outside the box, solve complex problems, and generate novel ideas.

4. **Enhancement of Problem-Solving Abilities.** Teaching problem-solving skills equips students with the capacity to tackle challenges effectively, both in academic settings and real-world situations.

5. **Development of Communication and Collaboration Skills.** Emphasizing communication and collaboration skills helps students work effectively in teams, express their ideas clearly, and engage in constructive dialogue.

6. **Adaptation to Technological Advancements.** Educating students on technological literacy ensures they can leverage digital tools, navigate online resources, and adapt to emerging technologies.

7. **Encouragement of Lifelong Learning.** 21st-century skills promote a growth mindset, encouraging students to embrace continuous learning, acquire new knowledge, and adapt to evolving circumstances.

8. **Preparation for Global Citizenship.** Cultivating global awareness and cultural competence prepares students to engage with diverse perspectives, respect different cultures, and contribute positively to a globalized world.

9. **Empowerment of Student Agency.** Teaching 21st-century skills empowers students to take ownership of their learning, pursue their interests, and become self-directed learners.

10. **Alignment with Future Trends.** As technology and society evolve, teaching 21st-century skills ensures that education remains relevant and responsive to emerging trends and needs.

By integrating the teaching of 21st-century skills into the education system, educators prepare students to navigate an increasingly complex, interconnected, and dynamic world, empowering them to succeed academically, professionally, and personally in the 21st century and beyond.

Methodology

How can we effectively incorporate these skills into our curriculum?

We can use the following strategies to integrate 21st century skills into the curriculum:

1. **Compilation of the curriculum.** Opportunities to introduce 21st century skills through cross-curricular interactions and project-based learning are identified within the existing curriculum.

2. **Project-based education.** Designing hands-on projects that engage students in critical thinking, collaboration, and creativity allows students to apply 21st century skills in real-world situations.

3. **Inquiry-based education.** Engaging students in questioning, exploring topics of interest, and self-directed learning, fostering curiosity and problem-solving skills.

4. **Integration of technologies.** Incorporate digital tools and resources into lessons to improve technology literacy, information literacy, and communication skills.

5. **Cooperation activities.** Facilitate group work, discussions and collaborative learning experiences to develop teamwork, communication and interpersonal skills.

6. **Evaluation strategies.** Develop assessment methods that assess student proficiency in 21st century skills, such as rubrics, portfolios, and assignments.

7. **Professional development.** Provide ongoing training and support to teachers to effectively integrate 21st century skills into their teaching practice and curriculum development.

8. **Community cooperation.** Collaborate with external organizations, professionals, and community members to create authentic learning experiences that promote global awareness and cultural competence.

9. **Student-oriented approaches.** Empowering students to take ownership of their own learning, set goals and reflect on their success, and develop self-regulation and metacognitive skills.

10. **Flexibility.** Apply flexibility in the curriculum to accommodate student interests, emerging trends, and different learning styles, and develop flexibility and resilience.

By implementing these strategies, teachers can effectively integrate 21st century skills into the curriculum, creating a learning environment that allows students to develop the critical competencies needed to succeed in the modern world.

Examples of Integrating 21st Century Skills into the Curriculum

Here are some examples of how 21st century skills are integrated into the curriculum:

Mathematics: Instead of traditional problem sets, students work on real-world math problems that require critical thinking, collaboration, and communication to solve.

Utilizing digital tools and simulations to explore mathematical concepts, promoting digital literacy and problem-solving skills.

Language Arts: Students engage in collaborative writing projects where they work together to create and edit stories or essays.

Incorporating multimedia elements into presentations or book reports to enhance communication skills and digital literacy.

Science: Conducting hands-on experiments that encourage students to think critically, analyze data, and draw conclusions.

Collaborating on research projects or debates about current scientific issues to develop critical thinking and communication skills.

Social Studies: Studying global issues and perspectives to promote cultural awareness and understanding.

Engaging in debates or simulations of historical events to enhance critical thinking, communication, and empathy.

Art and Music: Encouraging students to express themselves creatively through various art forms and music compositions.

Collaborating on group art projects or performances to develop teamwork and communication skills.

Physical Education: Implementing cooperative games and team sports that require communication, collaboration, and problem-solving.

Encouraging students to set goals, track progress, and reflect on their physical fitness and well-being.

Career and Technical Education (CTE): Providing hands-on projects and internships that simulate real-world work environments.

Developing skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, communication, and teamwork in a specific career field.

By integrating 21st century skills across various subjects in the curriculum, educators can prepare students to succeed in an increasingly complex and interconnected world.

General conclusions

By integrating 21st century skills across the curriculum, educators can prepare students to succeed in an increasingly complex and interconnected world.

In general education schools, we can use strategies to develop 21st century skills of students:

1. **Add project-based learning.** Develop projects that encourage students to collaborate, think critically, solve problems, and communicate effectively while working on real-world tasks.

2. **Development of critical thinking.** Encourage students to analyze information, evaluate sources, and think creatively to develop solutions to complex problems.

3. **Education of creativity.** Provide opportunities for students to express their ideas, explore different perspectives, and engage in activities that encourage creativity and innovation.

4. **Encouraging cooperation.** Facilitate group work, discussion, and peer interaction to help students learn to work effectively in teams, express opinions, and respect different points of view.

5. **Integration of technology.** Use digital tools and resources to enhance the learning experience, develop technological literacy, and prepare students for the digital age.

6. **Development of communication skills.** Teach students to express themselves clearly, listen actively, and communicate respectfully to improve their communication skills.

7. **Develop problem-solving skills** h. Provide opportunities for students to identify problems, explore multiple solutions, and implement strategies to overcome challenges.

8. **Development of information literacy.** Teach students how to find, evaluate, and use information from a variety of sources to improve their research and analytical skills.

9. **Formation of cultural competence.** Promote cultural awareness, diversity, and inclusion to help students appreciate different cultures, perspectives, and backgrounds.

10. **Promote global awareness.** To introduce students to global problems, encourage them to think on a global scale, and foster a sense of responsibility in solving global problems.

By incorporating these strategies into mainstream schools, educators can effectively develop 21st century skills in students, preparing them to succeed in a rapidly changing world and become lifelong learners with the necessary competencies for the future.

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